

Effects of Interfacial Reaction on Fracture Mode and Tensile Strength of Fibres in Metal Matrix Composites

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To describe the effects of interfacial reaction between the fibre and matrix on tensile behaviour of composites, a model was presented on the basis of the mechanism that a notch is formed due to fracture of the reaction layer and it extends into fibre, resulting in loss in composite strength. This model was applied to the reported data of W/Al, B/Ti₄O₄, B/Ti₇Si₃, B/Al, Mo/3003Al, GF/6061Al, B/SiC and W/Cu-5%Co in which reaction layers are formed. The fracture mode and tensile strength of fibres in these composites with reaction layers on the fibre surfaces were described well by this model in a quantitative manner as a function of thickness of reaction layers and as a function of annealing temperature and time.

INTRODUCTION

In most artificial metal matrix composites, as fibres and matrix are consolidated in a thermodynamically non-equilibrium state, interfacial chemical reaction between fibres and matrix often takes place when composites are exposed at high temperatures. The interfacial reaction has been known as one of the causes in degrading mechanical properties of composites. To account for this degradation, several mechanisms have been offered; (a) notch formation due to premature fracture of the reaction layer, (b) roughening of fibre surface, (c) degradation of intrinsic properties of fibre and/or matrix, (d) decrease in effective cross-sectional area of fibre and so on. Among them, the degradation mechanism of (a) has been observed in many composite systems (1 to 6). On the basis of this degradation mechanism, the present authors (7, 8) have proposed a theoretical model to describe the fracture mode and strength of fibre σ_{fu} as a function of the thickness of reaction layer. As the thickness of the reaction layer, c , is able to be expressed in terms of annealing time t and temperature T , it is possible to formulate the variation of σ_{fu} of fibre with reaction layer as a function of t and T , by modifying the original model. The original or modified model has been applied to various kinds of annealed composite systems, and it has been found that the experimental data of W/Al reported by Ochiai and Murakami (9), B/Ti₄O₄ and B/Ti₇Si₃ by Metcalfe and Klein (2), B/Al by Ochiai et al (10), B/6061Al by Metcalfe and Klein (2), Wright and Intwala (11) and Olsen and Tompkins (12), Mo/3003Al by Heitman et al (3), GF(graphite fibre)/6061Al by Khan (5), B/SiC by Shorshorov et al (13) and W/Cu-5%Co by Petrusek and Weeton (6) could be well described by the model. This paper presents the results of application of the model to the aforementioned composites. The reaction layer for each composite, forming at fibre-matrix interface at elevated temperatures, are shown in

Table 1 The composite systems on which the present model have been applied and their reaction layers , together with the results of the application.

Composite (Reference)	Reaction Layer	Sequence among Unifying Parameters in Region II	σ_{fu} in Region II	Fracture Mode* in Region II
W/Al (9)	WAl ₁₂	Region II does not exist due to $\sigma_{fu}^{\circ} > \sigma_f^* > \sigma_f^{\Delta}, \sigma_f^{\ominus}$	σ_{fu}°	I
B/Ti40A (2)	TiB ₂	$\sigma_{fu}^{\circ} > \sigma_f^* > \sigma_f^{\ominus}$ and $\sigma_f^{\Delta} > \sigma_f^*$	σ_f^*	II
B/Ti75A (2)	TiB ₂			
B/Al (10)	AlB ₂			
B/6061Al (2,11,12)	(Al,Mg)B ₂			
Mo/3003Al (3)	Al ₅ Mo	$\sigma_{fu}^{\circ} > \sigma_f^{\ominus} > \sigma_f^*$ and	σ_f^{\ominus}	III
GF/6061Al (5)	Al ₄ C ₃			
W/Cu-5%Co (6)	Recrystallization			
B/SiC** (13)	-	$\sigma_f^{\Delta} > \sigma_f^*$		

- * Fracture Mode in Region II ;
- I : Notch formation at the stress level of σ_f^{\ominus} → Interfacial debonding at the stress level of σ_f^{Δ} → Fibre fracture at the stress level of σ_{fu}° .
 - II : Notch formation at the stress level of σ_f^{\ominus} → Notch extension into fibre at the stress level of σ_f^* .
 - III : Notch formation and simultaneous extension into fibre at the stress level of σ_f^{\ominus} .

** B/SiC ; Boron fibre coated with SiC layer. In this system, the SiC layer is regarded as the brittle layer.

Table 1 , where B/SiC is the boron fibre coated with SiC layer in which no reaction takes place but the data of this system can be analysed by the present model since the SiC layer can be regarded as a brittle layer as well as the reaction layers.

THEORETICAL MODEL

When the brittle layer on the fibre surface fractures at an early stage of deformation, a notch is formed on the fibre surface. The formed notch hastens a fracture of the fibre if the interface between the fibre and brittle layer is strong enough to permit the formed notch to extend into the fibre. On the other hand, if the interfacial bonding is weak and the exerted shear stress at the interface exceeds the interfacial shear strength, debonding occurs, which leads to no loss in fibre strength, because debonding causes blunting of the notch-tip. In general, the fibre strength σ_{fu} is determined by (i)when brittle layer fractures; namely when a notch is formed, (ii)when the notch extends into the fibre and (iii)when interfacial debonding arises. The stress levels of the fibre at the broken end of the layer, σ_f^{\ominus} , σ_f^* and σ_f^{Δ} , corresponding to (i) to (iii), respectively, can be obtained by using a model of two-component composite cylinder of inner core of fibre and outer sleeve of brittle layer, as shown in Fig.1 where r_p and z refer to the radius of fibre and the distance from the broken end of the layer, respectively.

When the outer and inner surfaces of the brittle layer are smooth as shown in Fig.1(a), it may be assumed that the brittle layer fractures due to its

intrinsic defects and the tensile strength of this layer follows the Weibull distribution, with the probability of failure at stress σ given by

$$P = 1 - \exp[-\bar{V}_b \{(\sigma - \sigma_u)/\sigma_o\}^m] \quad (1)$$

where m is the Weibull modulus, \bar{V}_b the volume of the brittle layer, σ_o the normalizing factor and σ_u the stress below which there is no probability of failure. The σ_u is, in general, very low and it is often treated as zero. The mean of the failure stress σ_{bu} , for $\sigma_u = 0$, is given by

$$\sigma_{bu} = \int_0^\infty \sigma f(\sigma) d\sigma = \sigma_o (1/\bar{V}_b)^{1/m} \Gamma(1+1/m) \quad (2)$$

where $f(\sigma)$ is given by $dP/d\sigma$, and Γ the gamma function. The fibre stress at a fracture of the brittle layer in the cross-section in which brittle layer fractures, $\sigma_f^{\otimes}(a)$, is given by

$$\sigma_f^{\otimes}(a) = \sigma_{bu} (E_f V_f + E_b V_b) / E_b V_b = \sigma_o (1/\bar{V}_b)^{1/m} \Gamma(1+1/m) (E_f V_f + E_b V_b) / E_b V_b \quad (3)$$

where E is the Young's modulus, V the volume fraction and the subscripts f and b refer to fibre and brittle layer, respectively. On the other hand, when the surface of the brittle layer is not smooth, as shown in Fig.1(b), the layer fractures due to stress concentration at the irregularities on the surface. Taking the depth of the irregularities as c , the strength of the layer is, to a first approximation, given by $(1/Y_1)(E_b G_{c,b}^*/\pi c)^{1/2}$ where Y_1 is the finite width correction factor and $G_{c,b}^*$ the critical strain energy release rate of the layer. Then the fibre stress at $z=0$ is given by

$$\sigma_f^{\otimes}(b) = (1/Y_1)(E_b G_{c,b}^*/\pi c)^{1/2} (E_f V_f + E_b V_b) / E_b V_b \quad (4)$$

We are interested in the region of small c , because the σ_{fu} is seriously reduced even if c is small enough compared to r_f (1 to 4). Taking c/r_f as nearly zero, eqs.(3) and (4) are simplified to

$$\sigma_f^{\otimes}(a) = \sigma_o (\pi d \ell)^{-1/m} (E_f/E_b) \Gamma(1+1/m) c^{-1/m} \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma_f^{\otimes}(b) = (1/Y_1)(E_b G_{c,b}^*/\pi c)^{1/2} (E_f/E_b) \quad (6)$$

where ℓ is the gauge length. The stress level of fibre, σ_f^{\otimes} , at which the layer fractures, is given by the lower value between $\sigma_f^{\otimes}(a)$ and $\sigma_f^{\otimes}(b)$, depending on the largeness of c_a . When c_a is smaller than a critical value of $c_{a,crit}$ given by

$$c_{a,crit} = \{1.12 \sigma_o \Gamma(1+1/m)\}^{-2} (E_b G_{c,b}^*/\pi)^{2/m} c^{2/m} \quad (7)$$

which is obtained by equating eq.(5) and eq.(6) and setting $c/c_a \approx 0$ namely $Y_1 = 1.12$, the brittle layer fractures by its intrinsic defects and σ_f^{\otimes} is given by $\sigma_f^{\otimes}(a)$, while, when $c > c_{a,crit}$, it fractures due to the surface irregularities and σ_f^{\otimes} is given by $\sigma_f^{\otimes}(b)$.

On the basis of the fracture mechanical concept, the σ_f^* is given by

$$\sigma_f^* = (1/Y_2)(E_f G_c^*/\pi c)^{1/2} \quad (8)$$

where Y_2 is the finite width correction factor and G_c^* the critical strain energy release rate. For $c/r_f \approx 0$, eq.(8) is reduced to

$$\sigma_f^* = (1/1.12)(E_f G_c^*/\pi)^{1/2} c^{-1/2} \quad (9)$$

By modifying the shear lag analysis, the σ_f^Δ is derived for the configuration of (a) in Fig.1 as (7,8)

$$\sigma_f^\Delta = \tau^\Delta E_f \{2\pi r_f (G_b \bar{r}_f + G_f \bar{r}_b) (1/A_b E_b + 1/A_f E_f) / G_f G_b\}^{1/2} \quad (10)$$

where τ^Δ is the interfacial shear strength, G the shear modulus, A the cross-

sectional area, \bar{r}_b and \bar{r}_f the distances of centroids of brittle layer and fibre from the interface, respectively. For $c/r_f \approx 0$, eq.(10) is reduced to

$$\sigma_f = \tau^\Delta E_f \{r_f(2-\sqrt{2})/2E_b G_f\}^{1/2} c^{-1/2} \quad (11).$$

For the conguration of (b) in Fig.1, an approximate derivation of σ_f^Δ can be made in a similar manner, if c is small compared to c . In this case, σ_f^Δ has the same form as eq.(11), except that c is replaced by $c-c_a$.

Fig.1 Model composite cylinder.

Denoting the failure stress of bare fibre by σ_{fu}^0 , we can know which of notch formation, notch extension and interfacial debonding arises, by comparing the unifying parameters of σ_f^Δ , σ_f^* , σ_f^Δ and σ_{fu}^0 with each other, since the sequence of them, in principle, corresponds to the sequence of occurrence. However, the values of σ_f^Δ , σ_f^* and σ_f^Δ are calculated only mathematically so that we should give physical meaning when we interpret the calculated sequence as similarly as in our previous work(7,8). For instance, when the calculated sequence is $\sigma_{fu}^0 > \sigma_f^* > \sigma_f^\Delta > \sigma_f^\Delta$, the mathematical meaning of this sequence is that, notch is formed at first, then debonding occurs and then notch extension occurs, but in actual behaviour, each event does not occur such a way, and we should interpret this sequence as follows; notch is formed at first, then debonding occurs, and after debonding, no notch extension occurs due to blunting of the notch-tip, which makes the notch unable to enter the fibre. In this case, the strength of the model composite σ_c is given by σ_{fu}^0 and that of fibre by σ_{fu}^0 . When $\sigma_{fu}^0 > \sigma_f^\Delta > \sigma_f^*$, σ_f^Δ , the formed notch extends at once if $\sigma_f^\Delta > \sigma_f^*$, and debonding occurs at once if $\sigma_f^* > \sigma_f^\Delta$, as soon as the notch is formed, since the conditions for the notch to extend and those for the interface to fail are satisfied with upon a formation of the notch. In the former case σ_c is $\epsilon_{bu} E_b$ (ϵ_{bu} : failure strain of the brittle layer and E_b : Young's modulus of the model composite) and $\sigma_{fu} = \epsilon_{bu} E_b$, and in the latter case, $\sigma_c = \sigma_{fu}^0$ and $\sigma_{fu} = \sigma_{fu}^0$. There are 4!=24 sequences among the four unifying parameters and for each sequence, interpretation should be given similarly. For further details the reader may refer to our recent work(7,8). As the σ_f^Δ , σ_f^* and σ_f^Δ are functions of c , the sequence among these parameters varies with c . Then the failure mode and tensile strength of the fibre coated with brittle layer can be described as a function of c .

Here we would like to show that there is a critical interfacial bonding strength τ_{crit}^Δ for the notch to extend. For the configuration of (a) in Fig.1, equating eq.(9) and eq.(10), we have

$$\tau_{crit}^\Delta = 0.93(G_c^* G_b E_b / r_f E_f)^{1/2} \quad (12)$$

For the configuration of (b), it can be derived similarly. For $\tau^\Delta > \tau_{crit}^\Delta$, σ_f^Δ is higher than σ_f^* , which means that the notch extension occurs prior to debonding and the fibre strength is reduced. On the other hand, when $\tau^\Delta < \tau_{crit}^\Delta$, σ_f^Δ is lower than σ_f^* , which means that premature debonding occurs and the fibre strength is not reduced. Another interesting point derived from the present model is that, for $\tau^\Delta > \tau_{crit}^\Delta$, there is a critical thickness below which σ_{fu} remains constant, being equal to σ_{fu}^0 but beyond which it is reduced. This critical thickness c_c is given by

$$c_c = (1/\pi d l) (\sigma_o E_f / \sigma_{fu}^0)^m \{ \Gamma(1+1/m) \}^m \quad (13)$$

by equating $\sigma_{fu}^0 = \sigma_f^\Delta(a)$ for the case of $\sigma_f^\Delta(b) > \sigma_f^\Delta(a) > \sigma_f^*$, and

$$c_c = (1/1.12 \sigma_{fu}^0)^2 (E_f G_c^* / \pi) \quad (14)$$

by equating $\sigma_{fu}^0 = \sigma_f^*$ for the cases of $\sigma_f^\Delta(b) > \sigma_f^* > \sigma_f^\Delta(a)$, $\sigma_f^\Delta(a) > \sigma_f^* > \sigma_f^\Delta(b)$ and $\sigma_f^* > \sigma_f^\Delta(a)$

and $\sigma_f^{\otimes}(b)$. For the case of $\sigma_f^{\otimes}(a) > \sigma_f^{\otimes}(b) > \sigma_f^*$, if c_c is determined experimentally as a function of c , the c_c can be estimated by equating $\sigma_{fu}^{\otimes} = \sigma_f^{\otimes}(b)$. In this paper, the region for $c \leq c_c$ where no reduction in σ_{fu} occurs is described as Region I and the region for $c > c_c$ where σ_{fu} is reduced is described as Region II.

As the thickness of reaction layer is able to be expressed by the parabolic equation given by kt^n where n is a constant and k the rate constant, expressed by an Arrhenius type relationship, i.e., $k = A \exp(-Q/RT)$ where A and Q are constants and R the gas constant, the c is expressed by

$$c = A \exp(-Q/RT) t^n \quad (15)$$

If empirical equation for c_c is known as a function of t and T , we can express σ_f^{\otimes} , σ_f^* and σ_f^{Δ} as a function of t and T . By comparing these unifying parameters to know the sequence among them, we can describe the fracture mode and σ_{fu} of fibre as a function of t and T .

APPLICATION

The present theory has been applied to many composite systems. It has been found that the composite systems mentioned in Table 1 are described by the present theory. These composites could be divided into three groups according to the fracture behaviour of fibre; group I: W/Al, group II: B/Ti40A, B/Ti75A, B/Al, B/6061Al, Mo/3003Al and GF/6061Al and group III: W/Cu-5%Co and B/SiC. In group I, the interfacial bonding strength is lower than τ_{crit}^{Δ} and the sequence of $\sigma_f^{\Delta} < \sigma_f^* < \sigma_f^{\otimes}$ is satisfied with. In this group, debonding arises prior to notch extension and σ_{fu} is independent of c , being equal to σ_{fu}^{\otimes} . In group II, the σ_{fu} is reduced for $c > c_c$ given by eq.(14). This group has the sequence of $\sigma_f^* < \sigma_{fu}^{\Delta}$ and $\sigma_f^* > \sigma_{fu}^{\otimes} > \sigma_f^{\Delta}$ in Region I and that of $\sigma_f^* < \sigma_f^{\Delta}$ and $\sigma_{fu}^{\otimes} > \sigma_f^* > \sigma_f^{\Delta}$ in Region II. In this group, the reaction layer fractures and a notch is formed at the stress level of σ_f^{\otimes} but the formed notch does not extend into fibre in Region I, since the effect of intrinsic defects in the fibre is predominant over the formed notch, but the formed notch extends into fibre after further loading at the stress level of σ_f^* in Region II, since the effect of the formed notch is predominant over the intrinsic defects. The σ_{fu} is given by σ_{fu}^{\otimes} for Region I and σ_f^* for Region II. In group III, for $c \leq c_c$ given by eq.(13), σ_{fu} is equal to σ_{fu}^{\otimes} , but for $c > c_c$, σ_{fu} is reduced as similarly as in group II. However, the sequence in Region II is $\sigma_{fu}^{\otimes} > \sigma_f^* > \sigma_f^{\Delta}$, which is different from that in group II. In group III, a notch is formed at the stress level of σ_f^{\otimes} and the formed notch extends into fibre at once in Region II. The σ_{fu} is given by σ_{fu}^{\otimes} for Region I and by σ_f^{\otimes} for Region II. In Table 1, the results of application of the present model to each composite are summarized. In the following part, some results on the representative composites of W/Al of group I, B/Al of group II and B/SiC of group III will be briefly described.

W/Al Composite

In this part, the prime (') is used to distinguish the composite strength and volume fractions of the components in real composites consisting of three components (fibre, reaction layer and matrix) from those of the two-component model composite cylinder. The tensile strength of W/Al composite σ_c' as a function of c of the reaction layer of WAl₁₂ is shown in Fig.2. According to the rule of mixtures, as the reaction layer, being segmented, cannot carry the applied load, the σ_c' is given by

$$\sigma_c' = \sigma_{fu} V_f' + \sigma_m^* V_m' \quad (16)$$

where V_f' and V_m' are volume fractions of the fibre and the matrix, respectively, and σ_m^* is the yield stress of the matrix. In this composite, the bonding strength at fibre-reaction layer interface τ^{Δ} was 48.1MPa, obtained from the pull-out test. Substituting the appropriate values of $G_c^* = 115 J/m^2$ (4), $E_f = 412 GPa$, $G = 165 GPa$, $E_b = 80 GPa$ and $r_p = 250 \mu m$ into eq.(12), we have $\tau_{crit}^{\Delta} = 113 MPa$. The τ_{crit}^{Δ} is higher than τ^{Δ} , indicating that interfacial debonding occurs prior to notch extension. For such a weak interface, σ_{fu} is given by σ_{fu}^{\otimes} . Substituting the

separately measured values of $\sigma_{fu} = \sigma_{fu}^0 = 1.29 \text{ GPa}$ and $\sigma_f^* = 34.3 \text{ MPa}$ and the measured values of V_f^m and V^m at each c into eq.(16), we can know the variation of σ_c' as a function of c , as shown with a solid curve in Fig.2. The calculated curve agrees well the experimental values. In this case, the reduction in σ_c' with increasing c is caused by the decrease in cross-sectional areas of fibre and matrix.

B/Al Composite

Single boron fibre-aluminium matrix composite specimens were prepared by evaporating aluminium onto boron fibre(10). The specimens were isothermally annealed at 723, 773, 823 and 873K and then tensile-tested at room temperature. The reaction layer was identified as ALB₂ by the powder X-ray method. Fig.3 shows the measured values of σ_{fu} plotted against annealing time t at each annealing temperature, where each open point shows an average value for more than ten specimens. As the reaction layer fractures at an early stage of deformation, σ_{fu}^0 is lower than σ_f^* , although it was not confirmed, which of σ_{fu}^0 (a) and σ_{fu}^0 (b) gives σ_f^0 . The σ_{fu} is then given by

$$\sigma_{fu} = \sigma_{fu}^0 \quad (17)$$

for Region I and

$$\sigma_{fu} = (1/1.12)(E_f G^*/\pi)^{1/2} \{A \exp(-Q/RT)\}^{-1/2} t^{-n/2} \quad (18)$$

for Region II by combining eqs.(9) and (15). The critical time, t_c , below which no degradation occurs, corresponding to the time at transition from Region I to II, is given by

$$t_c = (1/1.12 \sigma_{fu}^0)^{2/n} (E_f G^*/\pi)^{1/2} \{A \exp(-Q/RT)\}^{-1/n} \quad (19)$$

The values of A , Q and n for this composite are not known to date, while the values of σ_{fu}^0 , E_f and G^* are already known to be 3.5GPa, 377GPa and 15.8J/m²(9), respectively. Then they were estimated as follows. First the measured values of $\log(\sigma_{fu})$ were plotted against $\log(t)$ for each temperature, and from the slope in Region II, n was found to be 1/3(c.f. eq.(19)). Then the measured values of σ_{fu} were plotted against $t^{-1/3}$. The slope in Region II in this plotting corresponds to $(1/1.12)(E_f G^*/\pi)^{1/2} \{A \exp(-Q/RT)\}^{-1/2}$, as known by eq.(18). Plotting the slope at each temperature against $1/T$, we obtained the values of $Q=61 \text{ kJ/mol}$ and $A=70.3 \mu\text{m}^2/\text{sec}$. Substituting these values back into eqs.(17) to (19), we can calculate numerically the variation of σ_{fu} as a function of t and T , and t_c as a function of T . The solid curves in Fig.3 show the result of the calculation, describing well the experimental results.

B/SiC(Boron Fibre Coated with SiC Layer)

Silicon-carbide is often coated on boron fibre to protect fibre from oxidation or from interfacial reaction. However, when the SiC layer is thick, fibre strength falls(13). This part deals with the variation of tensile strength of

Fig.2 The variation of σ_c' of W/Al composite as a function of c .

Fig.3 The variation of σ_{fu} of B/Al composite annealed at 723(a), 773(b), 823(c) and 873K(d) as a function of annealing time t .

boron fibre coated with SiC layer as a function of the thickness of SiC layer by using the data of Shorshorov et al(13) who reported the average tensile strength of the B/SiC fibre, $\sigma_{u,B/SiC}$, based on the total cross-sectional area of the fibre and SiC layer, as shown in Fig.4. As the interfacial bonding is considered to be strong, we need only to consider the sequences of $\sigma_{fu} > \sigma_f^* > \sigma_f^{\otimes}$ and $\sigma_{fu} > \sigma_f^{\otimes} > \sigma_f^*$ for the reduction in strength. Among these two sequences, the former sequence does not correspond to the present case due to the following reason. If $\sigma_{fu} > \sigma_f^* > \sigma_f^{\otimes}$ in Region II, σ_{fu} is given by σ_f^* , so that $\sigma_{u,B/SiC}$ is given by

$$\sigma_{u,B/SiC} = (V_f/Y_2)(E_f G^*/\pi c)^{1/2} \quad (20)$$

from eq.(8). In this case, as the values of c are not small enough compared to r_f , Y_2 should be given by $Y_2 = (1/2)(\xi)^{-1/2} \{1 + (1/2)\xi + (3/8)\xi^2 - 0.363\xi^3 + 0.731\xi^4\}$ where $\xi = r_f / (r_f + c)$. The broken curve in Fig.4 shows the result of calculation by using eq.(20) for Region II in which the reported values of $E_f = 372 \text{ GPa}$, $r_f = 50 \mu\text{m}$ and $G^* = 15.8 \text{ J/m}^2$ were substituted and $\sigma_{u,B/SiC} = \sigma_{fu}$ for Region I. The calculated curve shown with a broken curve in Fig.4 does not agree with the experimental results. It is evident that the sequence $\sigma_{fu} > \sigma_f^* > \sigma_f^{\otimes}$ for Region II is not the present case. Thus we need only to consider the sequence of $\sigma_{fu} > \sigma_f^{\otimes} > \sigma_f^*$ for Region II, which implies that the fibre fractures as soon as the SiC layer fractures in Region II. For this sequence, assuming that σ_f^{\otimes} is given by $\sigma_f^{\otimes}(a)$, the $\sigma_{u,B/SiC}$ in Region II is given by

$$\sigma_{u,B/SiC} = \sigma_o (1/\sqrt{v_b})^{1/m} \Gamma(1+1/m) (E_f V_f + E_b V_b) / E_b \quad (21)$$

The constants m and σ_o for this material are, however, unknown. These values were inferred from the reported data by plotting $\ln \sigma_{u,B/SiC} (E_b (E_f V_f + E_b V_b))$ against $\ln(1/\sqrt{v_b})$ whose slope in Region II corresponds to $-(1/m)$. Then $\sigma_{u,B/SiC}$ was calculated by $(\sigma_o/E_b)(E_f V_f + E_b V_b)$ for Region I and by eq.(21) for Region II as a function of c, as shown with a solid curve in Fig.4. The calculated curve describes well the experimental results. It has been reported that the tensile strength of the boron fibre itself is drastically reduced by prolonged deposition process of SiC layer. For instance, for $c = 8.5 \mu\text{m}$, σ_o is 2.24 GPa . However, also for such a thickness, $\sigma_{u,B/SiC}$ is determined by eq.(21), since even if G^* might be reduced, the sequence in Region II of $\sigma_{fu} > \sigma_f^{\otimes} > \sigma_f^*$ is retained. Thus the reported data of $\sigma_{u,B/SiC}$ for the total range of c could be explained by the present model.

In the present analysis, the fracture model of single fibre-brittle layer system has been applied to real composites consisting of multi-fibres and matrix, except for single boron fibre/aluminum composite specimens and B/SiC. However, to describe precisely fracture behaviour of multi-fibre composites, more factors such as distribution of fibre strength, stress concentrations arising from the fracture of weak fibres, triaxial stresses due to mechanical interactions between fibres and matrix, and so on should be taken into consideration. The present work gives only a frame work to describe the effect of interfacial reaction on tensile strength to a first approximation. The used equations in this work are, however, very simple, which makes it possible to estimate with ease the tensile strength and fracture mode of fibre coated with reaction layer as a function of thickness of the layer and as a function of annealing time and temperature, and also the present model seems to describe well the experimental results. In these points, the present model seems to be useful.

Fig.4 The variation of tensile strength of boron fibre coated with SiC as a function of c. (o: data of Shorshorov et al(13))

CONCLUSIONS

A theoretical model on fracture mode and tensile strength of fibres with brittle layers on their surfaces was presented. The proposed model was applied to various kinds of composites in which interfacial reaction takes place to form brittle layers on fibre surfaces. The present model described well the fracture mode and tensile strength of the fibres as a function of the thickness of reaction layers or as a function of annealing time and temperature.

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